

AUTOMATED COOLING SYSTEM TO PROTECT TRANSFORMERS AGAINST FIRE AND EXPLOSION

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As a result of the inability of the existing automated protection devices and systems to provide full and reliable protection of expensive high-voltage transformers, there are interruptions in the uninterrupted supply of energy to consumers [12-13]. From this point of view, it is necessary to use methods and devices based on new technologies that protect high-voltage transformers from emergency short circuits [15-16]. It is known that ensuring continuous operation of the transformer by continuous control and prevention of overheating of the dielectric cooling oil of high-voltage transformers, as well as its long-term operation at high power, is one of the most urgent problems of current continuous energy transmission [17-20].

If we analyzed the scientific research and engineering works carried out in this direction, for example, a method and device for early detection of the explosion of the transformer, created by Indian scientists, was proposed for preventive protection against the subsequent fire. This device consists of a case filled with coolant and pressure sensors placed inside it, which actuate valves and expel inert gases inside the case. Here, the pressure rise and pressure generator are not shown [2,3].

Also known is the device that protects the automatic connection network against the explosion and burning of the transformer at high pressure, and this device includes a gas relay, a sensitive electric relay, a special relay, a dielectric cooling tank, a control unit and a slot for releasing the nitrogen gas produced. Dielectric oil emits nitrogen gas during the cooling of the boiler, when the nitrogen gas is released, the gas relay and the sensitive electric relay are activated and send a signal to the control unit [4, 6-8].

The method and tool used in this device cannot fully satisfy the current need. Also, this device does not have a system of automatic disconnection and reconnection of the transformer in the event of a short circuit in the high and low voltage lines. The protection means of the proposed devices do not meet the current requirements. Protection devices of transformer devices have not changed significantly as the demand for energy supply has increased.

Taking into account the shortcomings of the above devices, in order to increase the efficiency of the protective devices of the transformer devices and ensure continuous operation, it is necessary to introduce tools that ensure continuous, high-power and long-time operation of the transformer by continuously controlling the temperature of the dielectric cooling oil and preventing overheating.

To achieve the given task, we present the block diagram of the device that protects and ensures continuous operation of the following transformer devices, as well as the device for protecting the transformer from fire and explosion (Fig. 1). The proposed transformer fire and explosion protection device includes a radiator, thermal relay and sensors made of pipes filled with cooling liquid placed inside its housing, as well as a pump that circulates the cooling liquid in the radiator and for additional cooling of the radiator from the outside of the transformer housing. the fan is placed.

It can be said that by continuously controlling and preventing the overheating of the dielectric cooling oil of the transformers, it is possible to ensure the continuous operation of the transformer and its operation at high power for a long time. The automatic transformer cooling system is a new system for detection and prevention of explosions and fires in electric transformers. Transformer failure is mainly caused by overheating of transformer oil and short circuit due to overloading. As a result of the inability of the existing automated protection devices and systems to provide full and reliable protection of expensive high-voltage transformers, interruptions in the uninterrupted supply of energy to consumers occur. In this regard, it is necessary to use methods and devices based on new technologies that protect high-voltage transformers from emergency short circuits. One such device is a transformer protection device against fire and explosion

The transformer protection device can be summarized as follows

- Reducing energy waste.
- Reducing the heat in the boilers resulting from overloading
- Extending the period of operation of plants
- Extending the working time by introducing a cooling system to the transformers
- To increase the capacity of the transformer by introducing a cooling system to the transformers.

We achieve reduction of oil waste in transformers. By extending the service life of transformers in the power transmission system, it is possible to reduce economic costs by up to 60%.